

A Digital Twin-Based Approach for the Optimal Deployment of Collaborative Robotics Applications

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Abstract— This paper proposes an optimization framework for designing collaborative robotics cells using a digital twin during the pre-deployment phase. The approach employs Bayesian optimization to iteratively find the optimal layout, integrating production and human-centric KPIs into the design process. The digital twin enables data-driven decision-making, reduces prototype costs, and ensures continuous improvement.

Index Terms—Human-robot collaboration, digital twin, Bayesian optimization, industry 4.0.

I. INTRODUCTION

The collaboration between humans and robots requires a significant change in how robots perceive, reason, and act. This change must address various levels of abstraction and reactivity.

Existing research generally focuses on improving the efficiency of collaborative cells that are already up-and-running. Although several studies have focused on task scheduling and assignment [1], but also to the planning and control phase [2–5], the main drawback concerns how the pipeline is initialized: these approaches often lack generality due to the sub-optimal starting design of the cell, which is usually not created based on the designer’s experience and without structured algorithms in mind.

Our goal is to optimize a collaborative process from the design phase. By integrating optimization techniques from the early stages of the deployment, it is possible to create collaborative cells that are intrinsically more efficient and better suited for human-robot interaction. The proposed technological solution consists of a flexible digital twin-based framework of the collaborative process, as shown in Fig. 1. The main contribution of our work is the creation of a black-box optimization framework where the cost function is represented by the selected target and is evaluated by running high-fidelity process simulations within a Bayesian optimization framework.

Using a digital twin to optimize the robotic cell before deployment offers several significant advantages, but the most important one concerns the accuracy in replicating human actions and identifying possible problems before constructing the physical cell, leading to a safer and more comfortable working environment for operators.

This abstract is a summary of the results presented in [6], while the use case presented in Section III is a first attempt in

Fig. 1. Closed-loop architecture presented: the simulation program can be used both as a *simulator* or as the *virtual replica* of the system.

applying the proposed architecture. An overview of the process is presented with the snapshots in Fig. 2.

II. APPROACH

The proposed methodology combines a high-fidelity human-robot simulator, Tecnomatix Process Simulate 2307 by Siemens, with a Bayesian optimization framework.

The implemented pipeline evaluates the cycle time for each design, informing subsequent iterations until the optimal layout is found. The primary objective is to minimize the cycle time while incorporating human-centered factors to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of each design iteration: in this sense, the overall collaborative process is also adapted to the necessities of the human operator, rather than considering only the optimal placement of the immaterial resources.

The Bayesian optimization algorithm navigates the design space using a Gaussian Process, iteratively refining the layout based on cycle time and other metrics. The process begins by sampling the search space in a representative way: for this purpose, 15 different layouts are selected. The optimization problem can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{x}_{\text{next}} &= \underset{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^D}{\text{argmin}} \hat{f}_{acq}(\mathbf{x}) \\
 &\text{subject to} \quad \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}) \leq \mathbf{0} \\
 &\text{by selecting} \quad \hat{f}_{acq} = \mu(\mathbf{x}) + \kappa \cdot \sigma(\mathbf{x})
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

As a function of how the exploration-exploitation trade-off (denoted with κ and representing a sigmoidal decay) is implemented in the acquisition function (denoted as $\hat{f}_{acq}(\mathbf{x})$)

Fig. 2. Example of a pick&packaging collaborative process based on the optimized layout.

Fig. 3. Reduction of the cycle time as the number of iterations increases.

and representing the Upper Confidence Bound function leveraging the mean value $\mu(\mathbf{x})$ and the standard deviation $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ of the augmented datasets), each candidate is a more refined version of the predecessor: this characteristic is what drives the algorithm towards the optimal solution in approximately 150 iterations (as shown in Fig. 3), accounting for boundaries on the search space \mathcal{X} and possibly non-linear Euclidean constraints $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x})$.

III. CASE STUDY

We implemented a case study involving a collaborative robot and a human operator performing pick and packaging operations, as shown in Fig. 2. The collaborative cell is composed of a Universal Robots UR5e, a Schunk EGK-40 gripper, and a Realsense D435i RGB-D camera for real-time human motion tracking. The equipment was virtualized on an external PC with ROS1-Noetic middleware for communication and control. The pick and packaging operations were modeled by taking into account the UR5e robot’s capabilities and interactions between the robot and the human operator. Tecnomatix Process Simulate allowed for the simulation of various task sequences, agent assignments, and real-time state adaptations, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the collaborative process.

The Bayesian optimization framework allows for finding the optimal configurations for the collaborative robotics cell. The

optimization variables included the robot’s mounting position on the table, the position of the objects to be picked, and the position of the placing boxes. The digital twin and Bayesian optimization framework identified optimal configurations, resulting in a significant cycle time reduction of approximately 18% with respect to the initial experience-based layout (that is represented by the result of the simulation for $k=0$ in Fig 3).

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This paper presents a novel approach to optimizing collaborative robotics cells using a digital twin during the pre-deployment phase. Future work will refine optimization algorithms and incorporate additional metrics like ergonomics and safety, together with the definition of a more informative Bayesian Optimization algorithm.

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